

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

Grant Agreement No: 101003766

**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

D4.4 Pilot studies demonstrating synergetic use of resources

Submission of Deliverable

Document information	
Work Package	WP 4 Research Optimisation
Deliverable No	D 4.4
Deliverable title	Pilot studies demonstrating synergetic use of resources
Version	FINAL
Dissemination level	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> PU - Public <input type="checkbox"/> PP - Restricted to programme partners <input type="checkbox"/> RE - Restricted to a group specified by the consortium <input type="checkbox"/> CO - Confidential, only for members of the consortium
Lead Beneficiary	MICINN (partner 2)
Contributors	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 1 – AWI, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 2 – MICINN, <input type="checkbox"/> 3 – UOULU, <input type="checkbox"/> 4 – ISP-CNR, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 5 – RCN, <input type="checkbox"/> 6 – EPB, <input type="checkbox"/> 7 - NWO, <input type="checkbox"/> 8 – DAFSHE, <input type="checkbox"/> 9 - CNRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 10 – UoS-CPS, <input type="checkbox"/> 11 – BAI, <input type="checkbox"/> 12 – UNIVIE, <input type="checkbox"/> 13 –IG-TUT, <input type="checkbox"/> 14 – WOC Europe, <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> 15 – BELSPO, <input type="checkbox"/> 16 – AMAP, <input type="checkbox"/> 17 – IGOT UL, <input type="checkbox"/> 18 - SPRS, <input type="checkbox"/> 19 – UKRI-BAS, <input type="checkbox"/> 20 – ITU, <input type="checkbox"/> 21 – USB, <input type="checkbox"/> 22 – RANNIS, <input type="checkbox"/> 23 – FAMRI, <input type="checkbox"/> 24 – ICR, <input type="checkbox"/> 25 – SPI
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Due date	30.09.2022
Delivery date	16.12.2022
Document history	
Creation Date	September 2022
Revision	V2
Revision Date	26.09.2022
Author	Andrés Barbosa
Status	<input type="checkbox"/> Draft <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> WP lead approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Coordinator approved <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Executive Board approved
Status date	16.12.2022

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101003766

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Bi- or multilateral sharing of resources in jointly operated logistics, infrastructure and programmes can help achieve more effective use of expensive equipment and capacities and thus reduce the costs in polar research. This report examines a selection of the existing and planned multilateral operations in the Arctic and the Antarctic using the experience gained from earlier joint cooperation networks. The selection of 4 pilot studies covers both Arctic and Antarctic research and logistics and are relatively large scale with several countries involved in the cooperation. The studies are the basis for demonstrating how bilateral or multilateral cooperation in joint research programmes and operations can provide added value to European Polar research and allow the more efficient use of resources. Each case describes the parties involved, historical background, the methodology and development, the added value and the benefits in scientific terms, logistics and the European dimension, as well as a proposal for translation to other polar spaces with a European perspective.

INTRODUCTION

This deliverable is part of the task 4.3 “Efficient use of resources due to jointly operated logistics, infrastructure and programmes” of the EU-PolarNet2 Work Package 4 “Research optimisation”. The goal of this task is to demonstrate how bilateral or multilateral cooperation in joint research programmes and operations can provide added value to European Polar research and allow the more efficient use of resources. It examines a selection of the existing and planned multilateral operations in the Arctic and the Antarctic using the experience gained from earlier joint cooperation networks. The selection of pilot studies was reached by consensus among the participants in EU-PolarNet2 and should cover both Arctic and Antarctic and that collaboration should be large scale and not for a particular scientific project. The pilot studies were also chosen considering that more than 2 countries should be involved. The selected initiatives included cooperation involving research vessels (Desk Pilot Study 1, Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium – ARICE), research stations (Desk Pilot Study 2, Ny-Ålesund Research Station), logistics movements (Desk Pilot Study 3, Dronning Maud Land Air Network (DROMLAN)) and infrastructure sharing (Desk Pilot Study 4, Optimising infrastructures sharing efficiency in the Antarctic Peninsula region Task Force). Each case is described following the same template with a general description of the joint initiative, the parties involved, historical background, the methodology and development, the added value and the

benefits in scientific terms, logistics and the European dimension and finally a proposal of translation to other different polar spaces with a European perspective.

1. Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium (ARICE)

General description of the joint initiative

ARICE's overall aim is to provide Europe with better capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean. ARICE aims at reaching this goal with the existing polar fleet by:

Networking, ARICE develops strategies to ensure the optimal use of the existing polar research vessels at a European and international level. The aim is to establish an International Arctic Research Icebreaker Consortium which shares and jointly funds ship time for scientists on the available research icebreakers.

Transnational Access, ARICE has provided transnational access to four European and two international research icebreakers. Access is granted based on scientific excellence of the research proposals, which researchers need to submit during the application process. The participating icebreakers are:

- PRV Polarstern, Germany
- IB Oden, Sweden
- RV Kronprins Haakon, Norway
- MSV Fennica, Finland
- CCGS Amundsen, Canada
- RV Sikuliaq, United States of America

ARICE is improving the research icebreakers' services by working closely together with the maritime industry on a so called "ships and platforms of opportunity" programme. Through this programme, commercial vessels operating in the Arctic Ocean will collect oceanic and atmospheric data on their cruises. At the same time, science and industry are working together to explore new technologies, which can improve ship-based and autonomous measurements in the Arctic Ocean. ARICE has also implemented virtual and remote access of data via an innovative 3D Virtual Icebreaker, which provides anyone with real-time information from the Arctic.

The Parties involved

Fifteen partners from twelve countries including European as well as two North American partners from USA and Canada have joined forces to improve the capacities for marine-based research in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean.

The partners include:

- Representatives of institutions that own or operate research icebreakers in the Arctic
- Representatives of European nations with strong polar programmes
- Representatives of the industry operating in the Arctic

List of partners:

Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI, Germany)

Association of Polar Early Career Scientists (APECS) (AWI, Germany)

Swedish Polar Research Secretariat (SPRS, Sweden)

Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI, Norway)

Laval University (ULaval, Canada)

University of Alaska Fairbanks, College of Fisheries and Ocean Sciences (UAF/CFOS, USA)

Spanish National Research Council, Marine Technology Unit (CSIC-UTM, Spain)

Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR, Italy)

World Ocean Council (WOC, France)

Institute of Oceanology, Polish Academy of Sciences (IOPAN, Poland)

Finnish Meteorological Institute (FMI, Finland)

Centre national de la recherche scientifique (CNRS, France)

Natural Environment Research Council, British Antarctic Survey (NERC-BAS, UK)

National Institute of Aquatic Resources (DTU-AQUA, Denmark)

ARCTIA (Finland)

Historic background

Scientific demand

The scientific demand for marine-based Arctic research has increased substantially in the recent years. Future scenarios of Arctic sea-ice variation are needed, not only because of the importance of sea ice for the global climate, but also to better guide the future commercial development of the Arctic, which could

become much more intensive as sea routes through the Arctic open on a regular basis and for a longer portion of the year.

In 2016, the EU project EU-PolarNet launched a “Public consultation on polar research priorities” to verify that their compilation of research priorities was representing the national (European) interests. The consultation got 225 responses from European scientists, policy makers, industry and the civil society. Interestingly the majority of answers came from countries which do not own research icebreakers but which are developing strong Arctic programmes and are showing a high interest in Arctic marine research (Fig. 1.1). This reflects the high demand of icebreaker berths in Europe.

Figure 1.1. Pie chart showing the participation by country in the EU-PolarNet “Public consultation on polar research” (Source: EU-PolarNet project)

Researchers demand continuous and all year-round observations in Arctic waters, with an emphasis on winter observations, on the use of Remote Operated Vehicles (ROVs) and Autonomous Underwater Vehicles (AUVs) capable to navigate under or close to ice, and on sediment sampling systems, all of which need to be deployed with the help of icebreakers.

Because Arctic marine research is technologically challenging and very cost intensive, it is often beyond the capacities of one single nation. It can only be carried out in close scientific and operational international cooperation.

International fleet of heavy and medium-sized research icebreakers

The availability of suitable PRVs for investigations of the ice-covered Arctic Ocean is critical, because only a handful of RVs worldwide have sufficient ice class to penetrate into the central parts of the Arctic Ocean, even in the summer. Additionally, over the next decade, nearly all national marine polar programmes in Europe and beyond will enter into a time window of critical change for their infrastructure assets due to an ageing research fleet (Fig. 1.2).

Figure 1.2. Expected lifespan of the heavy and medium sized research icebreakers international fleet, when estimating an average vessel lifespan of 30 yrs. and correcting where midlife refit is reported. Legend: red, PRVs to be decommissioned within 3 yrs. from now; orange, PRVs to be decommissioned within 4-13 yrs. from now; blue, to be decommissioned within 14 to 27 yrs. from now; green, research icebreakers recently constructed. (Modified from EUROFLEETS2 project)

The only three heavy icebreakers currently available in the EU and associated countries are the IB Oden (PC-1-2, Sweden), the PRV Polarstern (PC-1-2, Germany) and the newly constructed RV Kronprins Haakon (PC-3, Norway). The three vessels are well equipped and truly multidisciplinary, but they are not able to satisfy the scientific needs in Europe. They cannot cover the key geographical areas all year round, because the RV Sir David Attenborough and PRV Polarstern operate on both poles, while the IB Oden operates as winter icebreaker helping to keep Sweden’s northern Baltic Sea free of ice for commercial vessels. In addition, the PRV Polarstern and the IB Oden are approaching the end of their lifespan and so far, there are no formal commitments to replace these infrastructures.

In addition to the three heavy icebreakers, the EU also operates in Arctic waters ice-strengthened RVs able to navigate in first year ice (IACS Polar Code PC4-PC7), and 5 ice-classified RVs, which are able to operate in open waters and ice conditions less severe than the ice-strengthened vessels. These vessels are therefore confined in their operational area at the ice margin zones.

The lack of coordination between heavy icebreakers, ice-strengthened vessels and ice-classified vessels also shortens the ship time availability of heavy icebreakers in the ice-covered Arctic Ocean because the heavy icebreakers are often used for research in the ice margin zones, while other vessels with less ice capacity could be used instead for that kind of research.

Methodology and development of the joint operated logistics, infrastructure or programmes

ARICE has provided transnational access or cross border access to the central Arctic Ocean in a set of international icebreakers. For this, ARICE opened calls for proposals that allowed to apply simultaneously to these vessels. The joint evaluation system, accepted by all operators, has been proved transparent and fair and ARICE succeeded to give access to a total of 8 research projects.

In this way, scientists based in countries that do not own or operate research icebreakers, or whose infrastructures operate in different areas of the Arctic Ocean, were able to access vessels that otherwise impossible to access through their national systems.

The calls for proposals are managed by ARICE through a single-entry submission portal. The proposal management and evaluation system has been accepted by the operators of all involved research icebreakers, and it has been proved to be fair and transparent, as per consultation to applicants (both successful and unsuccessful) and reviewers.

The proposals are implemented as joint cruises, where the team funded by ARICE joins other participants in reaching their research area. This avoids travelling back and forth to port areas while optimising the cruise routes and transects.

Main overall results and added value of the cooperation

Results: Transnational access

ARICE has implemented eight transnational access cruises to research icebreakers in the High Arctic giving access to 39 researchers in person and 28 in remote. The ARICE funded cruises have been led by researchers from countries that either do not operate research icebreakers, or whose national icebreaker operates in different regions.

ARICE funded cruises - operational areas

Figure 1.3. Geographic location of the ARICE funded cruises

Figure 1.4. Researchers involved in the ARICE funded cruises. a) in person vs remote access; b) Male, female and number of early career scientists irrespective of their gender

Results: increased international cooperation

As a minimum of three nations had to be involved in the submitted applications, this has led to very multidisciplinary and multinational teams.

Figure 1.5. Nationalities researchers involved in ARICE funded cruises

Through the networking activities in ARICE, the operators of research icebreakers have been brought together in discussion to optimise the polar fleet.

Discussion

Description of the benefits in scientific terms

The benefits of cooperation among research icebreakers and the transnational access to these infrastructures can be divided into:

- increased ship-time availability
- increased research collaborations
- better use of the European intellectual capital and knowledge transfer
- optimisation of resources

Transnational access represents a game changer for many nations that, despite of having strong polar programmes, do not have access to this kind of infrastructure.

Thanks to the ship time optimisation (longer cruises, on board multidisciplinary, international teams) ship time has been maximised by adapting the ship transects to serve all onboard proposals.

Since a minimum of three nations had to be involved in the submitted applications, this has led to very multidisciplinary and multinational teams. These long cruises have resulted in strengthened research

networks and collaborations that will be maintained in the near future, as expressed by cruise participants.

Through the networking activities in ARICE, the operators of research icebreakers have been brought together in discussion to optimise the polar fleet.

Identification of barriers

This cooperation and networking among operators of research icebreakers has resulted in an understanding of the barriers that hamper an optimal use of these costly research infrastructures.

1. Limited number of infrastructures
2. Different level of infrastructure demand, associated to national access funding/support level
3. Both poles perspective of research icebreakers (long transits) and logistic duties (i.e. serving Antarctic bases)
4. Adequate use of the research icebreakers (right vessel in the right place)
5. Overlapping among the research programmes /lack of coordination
6. Limited or insufficient communication among operators in their planning phase.
7. Different planning times for the different infrastructures
8. No permanent and sustained transnational access mechanism for researchers

A brief proposal about how these pilot initiatives can be translated to other polar spaces

The polar fleet operating in the Antarctic region suffers the same barriers of access and lack of coordination than the Arctic fleet. A better collaboration between Antarctic or polar programmes in this area would also benefit and optimise the available infrastructure and the access to it.

Sharing of resources and increased communication among operators and polar programme managers would lead to a better infrastructure planning to fulfil European research goals in contribution to a strengthened European Research Area. In addition, a sustained transnational access European system would ensure that the European intellectual capital is fully utilised.

2. Ny-Ålesund Research Station - Monitoring, understanding and explaining Arctic systems and global changes at 79°N

General description of the joint initiative

Developing and maintaining high Arctic research infrastructure comes with a considerable cost. There is, however, also a considerable upside in that such infrastructure makes high latitude research and monitoring more efficient (and thus, relatively less expensive), and in that it makes it possible to monitor, understand and explain Polar systems and global changes.

Ny-Ålesund Research Station (NyÅ RS), located at 79°N on the shore of Kongsfjorden (Svalbard, Norway), is a prime example of how national (in this case, Norwegian) commitment over several decades, combined with shorter term investments by research institutions in staff, equipment and projects, combine to deliver some of the longest time series recorded anywhere in the Arctic of glacier mass balance, atmospheric parameters, bird and mammal population dynamics, etc. - some of them going back more than 50 years, and all of them providing unique insight into a changing Arctic environment.

<http://svalbardkartet.npolar.no>

The parties involved

Today, 18 institutions from 11 countries have a permanent/recurring presence, either with year-round activity and staff, or through seasonal activities. Ny-Ålesund Science Managers Committee (NySMAC¹) provides an arena for these institutions to coordinate research activity, and to discuss research infrastructure development. Additional institutions from even more countries have less regular, project-based activity at Ny-Å RS. NySMAC also played a key role in the development of the four broad and dynamic flagship programmes, covering activities related to *Atmosphere*, *Glaciology*, *Terrestrial ecology*, and *The Kongsfjorden system* (marine research).

- Alfred Wegener Institute (AWI), Germany
- Andøya Space (AS), Norway
- Chinese Arctic and Antarctic Administration (CAA), China
- German Research Centre for Geosciences (GFZ), Germany
- Korea Polar Research Institute (KOPRI), Republic of Korea
- National Centre for Polar and Ocean Research (NCPOR), India
- National Institute of Polar Research (NIPR), Japan
- Natural Environment Research Council (NERC), UK
- NILU – Norwegian Institute for Air Research, Norway
- Norwegian Mapping Authority (NMA), Norway
- Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI), Norway
- Norwegian Research Centre AS (NORCE), Norway
- Stockholm University (SU), Sweden
- The French Polar Institute (IPEV), France
- The National Research Council (CNR), Italy
- The University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS), Norway
- UiT – The Arctic University of Norway (UiT), Norway
- University of Groningen (UG), The Netherlands

1 <https://nyalesundresearch.no/nysmac/>

Historic background

While Ny-Ålesund's history includes mining, exploration and tourism, research and environmental monitoring has been the only full-time activity on-site since 1967. The European Space Research Organisation was instrumental in the establishing a telemetry station in 1967, and the Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) has had year-round activity in Ny-Ålesund since 1968.

With the exception of the building housing NPI, and the Zeppelin observatory, all buildings in Ny-Ålesund are owned by Kings Bay AS (KB), a company wholly owned by the Norwegian state. Institutions typically rent offices and accommodation from KB, and some also rent dedicated/exclusive laboratory facilities.

Methodology and development of the jointly operated logistics, infrastructure or programmes

One of the unique qualities of NyÅ RS is the access that all actors have to common infrastructure, common tools and common resources – ranging from joint laboratories, via detailed information in the Ny-Ålesund GIS system on where instruments and projects are located, to the utilisation of data that contribute to international programmes and networks. The *Research Strategy for NyÅ RS*² released in 2019 further emphasises the importance of continued development and more extensive use of joint facilities and laboratories. Furthermore, the Research Strategy points to the four flagship programmes as key arenas for discussing research priorities, and for providing input to future research infrastructure development. NySMAC has an important role in coordinating priorities across flagships.

² <https://www.forskningsradet.no/siteassets/publikasjoner/2019/ny-alesund-research-station-research-strategy2.pdf>

Photo: Helge T. Markussen, Norwegian Polar Institute

Main overall results and added value of the cooperation of the joint operated logistics, infrastructure or programmes

While NyÅ RS is a small part of the total area of the Svalbard archipelago, between $\frac{1}{8}$ and $\frac{1}{4}$ of all research activity on Svalbard as registered in the *Research in Svalbard* database³ takes place here - making it a "research hot-spot". This is reflected in the fact that approximately 100 peer-reviewed publications based on activity at NyÅ RS are published each year⁴.

One publication from 2022 - *Five decades of terrestrial and freshwater research at Ny-Ålesund, Svalbard*⁵ - illustrates two key traits that many of these publications share:

³ <https://www.researchinsvalbard.no>

⁴ <https://nyalesundresearch.no/research-and-monitoring/#publications>

⁵ <https://doi.org/10.33265/polar.v41.6310>

- 1) International and cross-disciplinary collaboration
- 2) The value that comes from being in one location for a long period of time, building data series that enable a comprehensive discussion of long-term trends and developments

Measurements of air quality, and of glacier mass balance have been going on in Ny-Ålesund for more than 50 years - facilitating the kind of in-depth understanding of climate change (mechanisms and effects) that very few other locations can provide.

Discussion

Considerable and consistent investment in NyÅ RS by the Norwegian government for more than half a century has provided the Norwegian and the international research community with a unique research platform at 79°N. Adding to this "baseline investment", a number of institutions have contributed consistently and substantially to the funding of long-term measurement series, campaigns and projects. The value that this creates in terms of scientific output (measured by publications) is considerable. Equally important, data from NyÅ RS is essential input to a number of monitoring programmes and networks:

- Baseline Surface radiation Network (BSRN)⁶
- Climate-Ecological Observatory for Arctic Tundra (COAT)⁷
- Global Atmosphere Watch (GAW)⁸
- Global Climate Observing System Reference Upper-Air Network (GRUAN)⁹
- Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW)¹⁰
- Global Terrestrial Network for Permafrost (GTN-P)¹¹
- Integrated Carbon Observation System (ICOS)¹²
- International Network for Terrestrial Research and Monitoring in the Arctic (INTERACT)¹³

⁶ <https://bsrn.awi.de>

⁷ <https://www.coat.no/en/>

⁸ <https://public.wmo.int/en/programmes/global-atmosphere-watch-programme>

⁹ <https://gcos.wmo.int/en/networks/atmospheric/gruan>

¹⁰ <http://globalcryospherewatch.org>

¹¹ <https://gtnp.arcticportal.org>

¹² <https://www.icos-cp.eu>

¹³ <https://eu-interact.org>

- Network for the Detection of Climate Change (NDACC)¹⁴
- Sustaining Arctic Observing Networks (SAON)¹⁵
- Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System (SIOS)¹⁶

Carrying out a research project in the Arctic or the Antarctic typically involves extensive preparations, and frequently takes the form of a complex expedition. By contrast, NyÅ RS is accessible by plane two days per week, and heavy equipment can be transported from the Norwegian mainland by a cargo ship that docks in Ny-Ålesund every 6-8 weeks. The savings in Euro following from this accessibility are impossible to quantify, but it is safe to say that they are substantial. The time saved is also difficult to quantify, but is - likewise - substantial.

The type of cross-institutional and cross-disciplinary collaboration that the review article on five decades of research in Ny-Ålesund is also the driving force behind projects such as *The future of Arctic coastal ecosystems – Identifying transitions in fjord systems and adjacent coastal areas (FACE-IT)*¹⁷. Funded through the Horizon Europe mechanism, and led by the University of Bremen, this project was "conceived" in Ny-Ålesund, and has activities in Ny-Ålesund as a key component going forward.

A challenge to all international research collaboration is that calls from national funding agencies aren't necessarily "coordinated" in what type of projects they fund any given year or project call. Researchers therefore often have to set up collaborative projects with "in-house" funding - a source that is typically restricted, and where the scope and duration of a collaborative project as a consequence is limited.

The Norwegian Research Council¹⁸, through the Svalbard Science Forum¹⁹, provides funding aimed at lowering these barriers to international cooperation through the Svalbard Strategic Grant - a seed money programme aimed at advancing coordination, collaboration and data sharing between researchers with a

¹⁴ <http://www.ndaccdemo.org>

¹⁵ <https://www.arcticobserving.org>

¹⁶ <https://sios-svalbard.org>

¹⁷ <https://www.face-it-project.eu>

¹⁸ <https://www.forskningradet.no/en/>

¹⁹ <https://www.forskningradet.no/en/svalbard-science-forum/>

relevance to Svalbard - and through the Arctic Field Grant - which supports fieldwork for students and researchers collecting data in Svalbard and Jan Mayen.

While it is fair to say that the research collaboration at NyÅ RS as judged by most metrics is a success, there is certainly room for improvement. Perhaps most pressing is the need for the development of an integrated monitoring programme bringing all the different research domains (and the research flagships) closer, and thereby giving added value to all of them. Securing open (and easy) access to all data generated is also a challenge.

SIOS (Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System) plays an important role in promoting data sharing / open access, and initiatives originating from Ny-Ålesund Research Station are coordinated with similar efforts initiated by SIOS.

A brief proposal about how these pilot initiatives can be translated to other polar spaces

Ny-Ålesund illustrates the value of combining (1) national (or, better still, collaborative) investments in common infrastructure, (2) joint or coordinated funding mechanisms for projects and long-term programmes, and (3) bottom-up discussions of research priorities and research infrastructure development.

Developing and maintaining a common research infrastructure platform comes at considerable costs. So does the establishing and maintaining of long time series, be they related to monitoring of greenhouse gases, glacier mass balance, or population dynamics of birds and mammals. However, NyÅ RS shows that these considerable expenses also bring with them considerable value in that they make high latitude research and monitoring more efficient (and thus, relatively less expensive), and in that they make it possible to monitor, understand and explain Polar systems and global changes.

While the development of Ny-Ålesund Research Station from 1967 to what it is in 2022, is obviously difficult to replicate, the lessons learned through this process can undoubtedly be translated to other locations in the Arctic and in the Antarctic. Long term commitment, baseline funding and common research infrastructure provide a unique platform for long-term or short-term projects and campaigns

with international, national or institutional funding. The model makes high latitude research and monitoring more efficient (and thus, relatively less expensive), and it makes it possible to monitor, understand and explain Polar systems and global changes.

Photo: Helge T. Markussen, Norwegian Polar Institute

3. Dronning Maud Land Air Network (DROMLAN)²⁰

General description of the joint initiative

The Dronning Maud Land Air Network (DROMLAN) is a non-profit, international cooperative project of the National Antarctic Programmes (NAPs) with stations and scientific interests in the wider Dronning Maud Land (DML) area in Antarctica.

The aim of DROMLAN is to facilitate inter-continental flights and intra-Antarctica flights to/from and within Dronning Maud Land (DML) to any member of COMNAP in science related activities, including logistics. The inter-continental flights connect Cape Town, South Africa with 3 established gateway runways in Antarctica, namely the Novolazarevskaya runway (hereinafter the Novo runway) and the Perseus summer-only ice runway, both managed by Russia and the Troll runway managed by Norway.

The air operations under this project mainly comprise the DML and the adjoining areas up to longitude of Halley Station in the west and the longitude of Syowa Station in the east and up to some stations operated by the DROMLAN members Russia and India at remote locations of East Antarctica.

DROMLAN map with stations of the members

²⁰ The DROMLAN pilot focusses on the historic cooperation and its development from 1998 until 2022 with logistics partly provided by Russian and Ukrainian aircrafts. Due to the current international sanctions on Russia, the use of the Novo airstrip has been scaled down in the 2022-2023 season. The Norwegian Troll airstrip is used as alternative.

The Parties involved

Belarus, Belgium, Finland, Germany, India, Japan, the Netherlands, Norway, Russia, South Africa, Sweden and the United Kingdom.

These 11 national Antarctic programmes outsource the operation of DROMLAN to the Antarctic Logistics Centre International (ALCI), a Cape Town-based private company. ALCI Nord, a Russian company, was created for the operation of the Perseus runway. Moreover, ALCI has its sister private company, The Antarctic Company (TAC), also based in Cape Town. TAC is responsible for the travel arrangement of non-governmental passengers, including private tourists, using DROMLAN's facilities.

The aircraft used for the inter-continental flights from Cape Town to Novo runway are Iluyhsin-76, owned and operated by Vorga Dnepr Airline, a Russian private air company. The aircraft used for intra-Antarctica flights include Basler-BT67 and Twin Otter DHC-6/300 owned and operated by Kenn Borek Air, an air company based in Canada, and Basler-BT67 owned by the Alfred Wegner Institute (AWI) and operated by Kenn Borek Air.

Iluyhsin-76 at Novo (Photo: M. Vancauwenberghe)

The users of DROMLAN are three categories. The first comprises members of national Antarctic programmes, who are considered priority users. The second category of users are members of government-funded scientific expeditions, but not organised by a national Antarctic programme. The third category of DROMLAN users are non-governmental passengers, including private tourists.

Historic background

Already in 1998, the European Polar Board expressed the need for long-range air support for European Polar research, both in the Arctic and Antarctic. Norway conducted the logistic/operational organisation for the Nordic Antarctic Programme during season 2000/2001. Polar Logistics, a UK based company, was charged to mobilise an aircraft IL-76MD with Ukrainian registration for three intercontinental flights between Cape Town and DML and there to a temporarily prepared blue ice landing strip at Henriksenskaeret - Blue One (71°19'S; 08°48'E). One of these flights in January 2001 was an evaluation flight joined by 20 experts from 8 countries. The flight evaluation report concluded that the work should continue to prepare for the establishment of an international network. One year later during the COMNAP meeting in Shanghai in July 2002, parties agreed to establish the International Corporate Dronning Maud Land Air Network (DROMLAN) as an umbrella for coordinated air operations in the long term. The Terms of Reference of this programme were adopted in 2003 and revised in 2010.

Methodology and development of the joint operated logistics, infrastructure or programmes

The DROMLAN members coordinated their efforts to get the necessary infrastructure in place, enabling to perform the multiyear, regular intercontinental flights between Cape Town and DML and to establish intra-continental flights to the various stations. DROMLAN members coordinated support beyond their national needs, in order to upgrade existing or to establish new facilities.

DROMLAN organises:

- Intercontinental air transport into DML from Cape Town
- Intra-Continental feeder flights to the various destinations within the DML area and beyond
- The shared services necessary to perform flight, cargo and passenger operations. In so doing, this collaborative structure aims to enable greater optimisation of the use of assets and resources of its national programme membership for the benefit of support to science.

Specific season prices are based on the following criteria:

- Number of flights needed
- Number of passengers given by the national operators
- Estimate for cargo transport given by the national operators
- Oil prices with an expected reasonable increase in price since last season

The costs of the flight operations are evenly shared by the DROMLAN members over the ticket cost by having an open book relation with ALCI and sharing the risk with them.

Each DROMLAN member prepared infrastructure at their respective station such as ski-ways, ground service, fuel storage and refuelling facilities, regular weather observations, communication and accommodation for transit passengers of the intra-Antarctic flight traffic. Additionally, the ship-borne delivery of aviation fuel is organised by the national programmes.

ALCI is responsible for the overall operation of DROMLAN including travel arrangements for the members of National Antarctic Programmes. ALCI charters the aircraft for inter-continental and intra-Antarctica flights from Vorga Dnepr Airline and Kenn Borek Air. The office staff provides all services for passengers such as environmental and pre-flight briefings, flight check-in as well as cargo storage, customs clearance, handling and loading for the intercontinental departures and arrivals, logistics in Cape Town, SAR/MedEvac (from Antarctica to hospital in Cape Town).

The Troll Airfield ice runway (71°57'S 002°28'E at 1,298m a.s.l.) is located close to Jutulsessen on a blue ice field about 7 km north of Troll station in DML. The runway was completed in 2005. Since then, it is mainly used for intercontinental national flights of the Norwegian Antarctic programme but also for DROMLAN missions. Because of the short distance between the airfield and the station all permanent staff for ground service and equipment needed for runway maintenance as well as for servicing aircraft is based at Troll station. DROMLAN passengers in transit are accommodated next to the runway in tents. The Norwegian Polar Institute (NPI) runs all facilities.

The Novo Airfield ice runway (70°50'39"S 011°35'44"E at 550m a.s.l.) is located at the inland ice plateau about 17 km southwest of Novolazarevskaya Station. During the summer-season the runway receives intercontinental flights and serves as the logistic hub for smaller wheel-ski aircraft flying to the destinations within DML and beyond. A summer technical base (ALCI-Airbase) is situated next to the runway to provide the ground services as: regular maintenance of the runway and passenger/cargo terminal for DROMLAN intercontinental and intra-Antarctic flights. The facility consists of mobile modules on sledges, providing accommodation for seasonal staff, aircrew and up to 75 passengers in transit. Novo Runway is jointly operated by the Russian Antarctic Expedition (RAE) and ALCI.

The Perseus summer-only ice runway (71°25'09"S 23°31'06"E) is located 60 km north of the Princess Elisabeth Station. The runway received its first intercontinental DROMLAN flight from Cape Town on 22

November 2019. The Perseus Runway mostly serves as backup for Novo airfield and is operated by ALCI Nord, a Russian company.

DROMLAN map with blue ice runways

At the respective DROMLAN member stations preparations such as ski-ways, ground services, fuel storage and refueling facilities, regular weather observations, communication, accommodation for transit passengers for the intra-Antarctic flight traffic are organised. The member NAPs also arrange the ship-borne delivery of aviation fuel to their stations.

The DROMLAN flight weather service was established at Neumayer Station III in cooperation between the Alfred Wegener Institute Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research (AWI) and the German Weather Service (DWD), providing to ALCI and the DROMLAN community daily products such as general weather forecast, DROMLAN Aerodrome Forecast (DAF), weather charts for the area and specialised consultations.

Main overall results and added value of the cooperation

The network was set-up within the collaboration spirit of the Antarctic Treaty. The benefits of the shared use of facilities, the shared (SAR) planning, the shared costs and the shared expertise are multiple.

For many countries, a similar organisation of logistics individually would not be possible. Together, there is enough critical mass to get logistics done in a cost-effective way. It allows for an optimal use of flight seats, thereby lowering as much as possible the costs and carbon footprint.

The sharing of experience/expertise in terms of aviation, logistics, safety and rescue, the combined use of logistics and fuel depots and a central coordination of the intra- and intercontinental flight planning and weather forecasting, enhances safety and provides the necessary continuity and flexibility in flight planning, taking into account the needs of all members.

Discussion

Besides the obvious positive aspects of sharing logistics efforts, there are also a number of caveats.

DROMLAN's operation involves various private operators. Flight operations are managed by ALCI and TAC, both South African private companies. The aircraft used for DROMLAN are owned and operated by two private air companies. 2 of the 3 airfields are in the hands of the private operator ALCI. Moreover, there are various actors or facilities with various nationalities involved in the DROMLAN operation. ALCI and TAC have South African nationality and the aircraft used for inter-continental flights and intra-Antarctica flights are registered in Russia and Canada. Novo and Perseus runways are managed by Russia and Troll Runway is managed by Norway. Overall, this makes permitting and notification of activities by the relevant Treaty partner states to the appropriate authorities complex.

Furthermore, the DROMLAN's facilities and service are used not only by governmental passengers but also by non-governmental passengers including private tourists. It is generally understood that non-governmental passengers can use the DROMLAN only if vacant seats are available and that the reason for allowing for nongovernmental passengers is to reduce the cost for governmental passengers. The different DROMLAN partners, national Antarctic programmes and private partners, deal with these tourism activities in different ways.

The National programmes are highly dependent on the private operator ALCI, both in terms of prices and services offered. There is no open competition with other possible governmental and/or private partners for the flight operations, possibly lowering prices and enhancing the services.

Last but not least, the DROMLAN services have been used by several Treaty inspections. It allows for very efficient visits of several stations by the inspection teams in a short period of time and even more to get access to stations which were difficult to reach before and/or without own logistic capacities. However, the surprise effect that normally accompanies these inspections is lost as the DROMLAN inter- and intracontinental flights for these inspections have to be booked months in advance and DROMLAN members therefore know about the planning (time and location) of these inspections at a very early stage.

A brief proposal about how these pilot initiatives can be translated to other polar spaces

DROMLAN can undoubtedly be seen as a good case study to coordinate and make more efficient logistic and research support by European national Antarctic programmes operating in a same region in the Arctic as well as the Antarctic.

However, in view of the above-mentioned arguments it requires careful consideration to maintain the operations intergovernmental, avoiding operations in the hands of a private operator.

Sources:

- DROMLAN annual reports
- Legal Issues concerning DROMLAN under the Antarctic Treaty System, Osamu Inagaki, The Yearbook of Polar Law Online, 13 Dec 2020
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4. Optimising infrastructure sharing efficiency in the Antarctic Peninsula region Task Force

General description of the joint initiative

This initiative has been promoted and funded by the Council of Managers of National Antarctic Programmes (COMNAP) and consists in the creation of sharing system of the infrastructures between different countries with scientific activity in the Antarctic Peninsula Region by implementing a bartering system that maximises the utilisation of Antarctic assets and reduces the money exchange.

The Parties involved

The parties involved were chosen to cover a wide range of sizes and circumstances, but all of them have relevant scientific activity, covering America, Asia and Europe. Included are National Programmes of:

- a) Chile, as a big programme which is one of the Antarctic Gateways for many Antarctic programmes worldwide.
- b) Korea, as a medium-large programme, with one station in the region and intense year around scientific activity.
- c) Poland, as a medium size programme, with a year-round station, but no ships or planes.
- d) Turkey, as a small newcomer to the Antarctic scientific activity but with vigorous science. They will set up their station in the region soon and still negotiating a ship service.
- e) Spain, medium-large size programme with 2 stations one camp and frequently two oceanographic ships.

Historic background

The initiative starts in 2018 and was funded by COMNAP in a 2-year period finishing in 2020. The purpose of the task force was to evaluate if there was any possibility of sharing infrastructures with the aim of reducing costs and investing that saved money on reaching more places and expanding the scientific limits of the programmes towards far reach locations. The idea emanates from an Antarctic region: Antarctic Peninsula in which almost 20 different countries operate with their own stations, ships and planes. The interaction among many of the partners is very fluent but normally organised in bilateral agreements, and sharing is common. However, such sharing is difficult in terms of balance and returning back the monetary debts. Even considering a normal bilateral interaction, the hypothesis was that there was room for more interaction, sharing and optimisation of the deployed infrastructures (ships, planes and stations),

Methodology and development of the joint operated logistics, infrastructure or programmes

The task force aimed at assessing the possibility of organising a bartering system for the infrastructures sharing in the Antarctic Peninsula region and evaluating the benefits of such system. The bartering system was inspired by the Ocean Facilities Exchange Group (OFEG), which uses a point system that allows a better organisation of assets sharing in oceanographic realm. The 'price' in points of the utilisation of different infrastructures is negotiated among the members and the points are exchanged among the users at medium term scale.

During the first year a reference for the unit point was agreed, which was a seat in a plane from Punta Arenas (Chile) to King George Island (Antarctica). Then the 'price' of the other shared facilities' (as container transport, ship days, berths at stations, etc.) was negotiated and fixed by consensus between the 5 groups.

Main overall results and added value of the cooperation

The main results of this exercise indicated that it was possible to create such a bartering system, avoiding the money exchange, and keeping the system open for further balancing in future seasons.

This exercise was done in 2018 over a previous season indicating good potentiality with an already working exchange of over 1,5 million € without promoting any exchange, and only between the 5 participants. In 2019, we have tried to test the system in a pilot season, but a flight accident reduced strongly the interactions, and then the pandemics came in 2020/2021, with a physical impossibility of launching the process.

Last Antarctic season, 2021/2022, the system was working, and data demonstrated that it can have a tremendous capability in the region, with effective exchange valued in several million € per summer season. This logistic, day to day interaction, would promote in a clear way the sharing culture and the proximity of different actors beyond the bilateral typical agreements.

Discussion

It is expected that with the incorporation of other actors (large and small programmes) working at the Peninsula region, we could promote a remarkable saving in logistics and related costs. This could be used for more science, triggering a clear benefit to the scientific activity in the region, reaching places further

with minimum costs. This activity will be reducing notably the carbon footprint of the national scientific programmes and providing a good atmosphere for diplomatic improvement among the countries.

The European dimension is limited to the European Partners operating there. We are only few European countries (Bulgaria, Germany, Poland and Spain, (UK, Ukraine) operating in the region, but the interaction with many others from North America (USA) South America (Argentina, Chile, Colombia Ecuador, Peru, Uruguay), and Asia (China and Korea), besides Russia, allows the European dimension being brought up and extend further away from our borders.

The first limitation that was expected was by the nationalistic claims of the countries participating (e.g. carrying the national flag around Antarctica). However, after a direct survey among the participants it was clear that if savings were put on the table, nationalistic trends could be left aside.

Perhaps the most serious limitation was the different timing for programming that the different countries have. This reduces the possibility of exchange because in some cases the programming of the season is completed 6 months before the activity and other require longer period of time, making the matching very difficult. This would require for sure a fine tuning among the programmes. However, we believe that the benefits are large enough to ensure a better exchange process.

Another difficulty could be the slow reaction that some national programmes can have in 'returning' the owed points. This, may produce destabilization of the bartering system.

A brief proposal about how these pilot initiatives can be translated to other polar spaces

A similar initiative is already taking place among 6 European national oceanographic institutions (OFEG) with remarkable success. The success of a similar initiative should be based on the volunteer character of joining the system, only those programmes interested and capable of sharing something should join the system.

This system could take place at different scales at both poles, Arctic and Antarctic, in regions typically visited by several operators (from the same or different countries) with a number of different assets, both stations and transportation units, as ships or planes. However, this system would only work if there is a long-term exercise with several seasons allowing balancing the accounts over the time.

The main conclusion that can be extracted after the analysis of the four Pilot Studies is a clear benefit in cooperation among the involved actors in terms of optimisation of resources. This cooperation leads to a net enhancement of the sharing culture between the participants.

The direct benefits that have been identified in these 4 pilot studies are:

- a substantial reduction of financial costs,
- an increased availability of time for using the infrastructures
- the possibility of carrying out activities not possible for a single country due to logistics limitations,
- increase of research collaborations including high inter and multidisciplinary and the international dimension,
- support for the establishment and continuation of long-term and monitoring studies of high interest in the study of global change,
- an improvement of the European knowledge transfer
- the contribution to the reduction of the carbon footprint.

Some difficulties or challenges have also been identified such as a limited existing infrastructure regarding research vessels, the need of an improvement of logistics coordination in the preparation of polar expeditions, the need of an improvement of research coordination through the national funding agencies to avoid overlapping of research and in some cases excessive dependency of private companies in a non-competitive environment advocating to maintain the operations intergovernmental.

In summary, these Pilot Studies clearly shows the benefits of integrated and coordinated actions for logistics and research in the Polar Regions, the space room for improving the existing joint activities and the potential for the implementation of similar specifically adapted joint actions in other infrastructures and Polar spaces.